

THE TEACHING EFFICACY, MOTIVATION, AND PERFORMANCE OF SECONDARY SCHOOL TEACHERS AS BASIS FOR A DIFFERENTIATED SUPERVISORY PROGRAM

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19813866>

ABSTRACT

This study examined the teaching efficacy, motivation, and performance of secondary school teachers in Quirino District, Quirino, Isabela, as basis for a differentiated supervisory program across the secondary schools in the district studied. Using a quantitative descriptive-correlational design, the study involved 93 teachers from five public secondary schools through total enumeration. Data were gathered using survey questionnaires and were analyzed through frequency and percentage distribution, weighted mean, chi-square test, and Pearson r. Findings revealed that the respondents came from varied fields of specialization, had differing years of teaching experience, generally carried the required teaching loads, mostly lived within 1 to 5 kilometers from school, and were moderately competent in ICT. Teachers were found to be highly efficacious in terms of student engagement, instructional strategies, and classroom management. Their level of motivation was moderate, while their performance for the last two school years was generally rated very satisfactory to outstanding. Statistical results showed no significant relationship between teachers' profile and their teaching efficacy, motivation, and performance, except for distance of residence, which was significantly related to instructional strategies. Likewise, no significant relationship was found among teaching efficacy, motivation, and performance. The study concluded that although teachers demonstrated high efficacy and satisfactory performance, these were generally independent of their profile variables. The findings highlight the need for continuous upskilling and reskilling, improvement of ICT competence, equitable distribution of teaching loads, and stronger supervisory support. Based on the results, a differentiated

supervisory program was proposed to enhance teachers' professional growth and instructional effectiveness.

Keywords: *teaching efficacy, teacher motivation, teacher performance, ICT competence, differentiated supervisory program*

INTRODUCTION

The quality of education affects how well children learn and is influenced by various inputs. In the Philippines, the quality of basic education, particularly student learning outcomes, has remained a major concern, prompting the Department of Education to launch Sulong EduKalidad in 2019 as a reform agenda for improving quality in a rapidly changing learning environment. Sulong EduKalidad is organized around the KITE reform areas: (1) K to 12 curriculum review and update, (2) improvement of the learning environment, (3) teachers' upskilling and reskilling, and (4) engagement of stakeholders for support and collaboration. According to DepEd, these reform areas are intended to directly influence student learning outcomes and strengthen the overall quality of basic education. Because these reforms are carried out largely through classroom and school processes, teachers remain central to the delivery of quality education (Department of Education, 2019a, 2019b).

Teachers sustain the educational system not only through mastery of subject matter but also through their capacity to help learners connect theory to practice. This broader role becomes more visible when teachers understand that teaching extends beyond mere content delivery to include motivation, pedagogical decision-making, learner support, and the effective use of instructional strategies. Research has shown that teacher motivation is closely tied to instructional choices and classroom practice, while teacher self-efficacy is positively associated with instructional quality and student motivational beliefs. In this sense, teaching effectiveness reflects not only what teachers know, but also how motivated and capable they are in delivering educational services to learners (Han & Yin, 2016; Burić & Kim, 2020; Hoy, 2021).

One of the earliest and most influential frameworks for understanding the relationship among teachers' beliefs, competence, performance, and learner outcomes is Bandura's social cognitive theory, particularly its concept of self-efficacy. This theoretical line helped explain why teachers' beliefs about their own capabilities matter for instructional behavior and student outcomes, and it also influenced the development of more systematic ways of measuring teacher efficacy. In teacher education research, this contributed to the development of quantitative instruments designed to assess key dimensions of instructional capability, including efficacy in instructional strategies, classroom management, and student engagement (Bandura, 1986; Tschannen-Moran & Woolfolk Hoy, 2001).

Research further indicates that effective teachers are better able to organize learning, manage classroom behavior, use clear instructional strategies, maintain engagement, and create a supportive learning climate. These dimensions of

effectiveness consistently appear in studies of teaching quality, which identify classroom management, clarity of instruction, activating teaching, differentiation, and teaching-learning strategies as core domains linked to student engagement and positive outcomes. Thus, teacher effectiveness is not a narrow trait but a multidimensional professional capacity reflected in how teachers plan, manage, adapt, and sustain learning in real classroom situations (Oliver & Reschly, 2007; Fernández-García et al., 2021; Klassen & Tze, 2014).

Although academic credentials, subject-matter expertise, pedagogy, and teaching techniques are all important in determining teacher competence, these alone may not sustain high-quality instruction in the absence of motivation and dedication. Research on teacher motivation shows that the quality of teaching is shaped not only by teachers' knowledge and skills, but also by their enthusiasm, commitment, and willingness to persist in the work of teaching. Put differently, instructional quality depends on both competence and motivational resources, since these together influence how teachers perform, respond to classroom demands, and support student learning (Han & Yin, 2016; Hoy, 2021; Tschannen-Moran & Woolfolk Hoy, 2001).

Moreover, motivation is crucial in influencing behavior in any organization. It affects output and performance at work. It is a need, want, or drive that organizes action and points it in the direction of a goal. It encourages someone to carry on with their career or activity as a human being. "Motivation is the ability to inspire people to do what you want because they want to do it," remarked former U.S. President Dwight D. Eisenhower. This suggests that individuals and their social environment interact to form motivation. (Martinez and Fule, 1997)

Motivation can be defined as the intrinsic and extrinsic drives or forces that determine focus, and direct behavior towards a specific target or goal (Gulnaz et al., 2015). Hence, it is an important factor in the promotion of teaching and learning excellence. Motivated teachers are more likely to motivate students to learn and to ensure the implementation of education reform. Therefore, the quality of an educational system cannot outperform the quality of its teachers (Nyakundi, 2012).

And this investigation is being undertaken in the same way. The purpose of the study was to find out why some teachers are more efficient and productive than others while others are less motivated to teach. The researcher has been leading a school for four years, during which time she has managed both new and experienced teachers. She has observed the effectiveness and efficiency of teachers in their formative years and has also watched how they gradually declined with time. When instructing, recently hired teachers are incredibly vivacious, passionate, assertive, and patient. However, it is noticeable that some of them lose some of their vitality, patience, and other traits as they get older in the department. And it is hoped that this study would prompt teachers to consider their motivation and assist them in regaining efficiency and effectiveness as they carry out their main responsibility of ensuring that their students learn.

The results of this study will serve as a foundation for future programs and projects to be developed and implemented by school administrators in order to provide school

heads with the necessary technical support. These initiatives may guide efforts to help newly hired teachers engage in upskilling and veteran teachers in reskilling in the competencies required to become effective facilitators of learning for 21st-century learners. Since educators must themselves possess these competencies before they can meaningfully develop them in others, readiness for 21st-century teaching remains essential to the successful transition of the educational process.

Research Questions

This study was designed to determine the teaching efficacy, motivation, and performance of secondary school teachers as the basis for a differentiated supervisory program. Specifically, it aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - a. field of specialization
 - b. teaching experience
 - c. teaching loads and other assignments
 - d. distance of residence from the school
 - e. level of ICT knowledge?
2. What is the teachers' level of teaching efficacy in terms of student engagement, instructional strategies, and classroom management?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the teachers' level of teaching efficacy and their profile?
4. What is the teachers' level of motivation?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the teachers' level of motivation and their profile?
6. What is the teachers' level of performance?
7. Is there a significant relationship between the teachers' level of performance and their profile?
8. Is there a significant relationship between and among the teaching efficacy, motivation, and performance of teachers?
9. What differentiated supervisory program can be designed based on the identified level of teachers' teaching efficacy, motivation, and performance?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used quantitative descriptive-correlational research since it provides answers to the what, how, when, and where questions. This research design is ideal for this study because it will examine or evaluate the relationship between a teacher's profile and their level of teaching efficacy, level of motivation, and level of performance among secondary school teachers in Quirino District, Quirino, Isabela.

Locale of the Study

The research was conducted in five public secondary schools of Quirino District where one school offers only Junior High School, another one offers both Junior and Senior High School and three schools offer pre-school, elementary, junior and senior high school.

Selection and Description of Respondents

The respondents of this study were the 93 high school teachers from the five (5) secondary public schools of Quirino District. Total enumeration was done in determining the respondents since the total number of secondary teachers in Quirino District is manageable. The distribution of the respondents is reflected in Table 1.

Table 1
Distribution of Respondents

School	Number
Quirino National High School	49
Rizal Comprehensive National High School	15
Sto. Domingo Integrated School	11
Dolores Integrated School	7
Villa Cacho Integrated School	11
Total	93

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher asked first for the approval of the Schools Division Superintendent of Isabela through channels before distributing the research questionnaires. After approval was granted, the researcher, through the school heads administered and retrieved the research questionnaire. Since Quirino was still considered a COVID-19 low-risk area during the time of floating of the survey questionnaire, face-to-face gathering of data was allowed by the higher ups though limited time was only given to the researcher. In this case, an overview of what the study was all about was communicated to the school heads and they were the ones who explained to the teachers as respondents of this study. Contact persons were chosen to facilitate the gathering of the needed data. For Quirino National High School which is considered a big school, the distribution was done by grade level to observe social distancing. Health protocols were strictly observed and applied during the conduct of said activity.

Statistical Treatment of Data

All of the collected data were analyzed using the following statistical tools.

Frequency and percentage distribution. These were used to analyze the profile of the respondents and their level of performance.

Weighted mean. This was utilized to analyze the teachers' level of ICT competence, level of teaching efficacy, and level of motivation.

Chi-square test. To determine the significant relationship between the teachers' level of teaching efficacy and their profile, the chi-square test was employed.

Pearson r test. This was used to find out if there is a significant relationship between and among teaching efficacy, motivation, and performance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Profile of the Respondents
 - a. Field of Specialization

Table 2
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in Terms of their Field of Specialization

Field of Specialization	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
English	14	15.05
Filipino	12	12.90
Science	13	13.98
Mathematics	18	19.35
Aral. Panlipunan	13	13.98
Tech. & Home Econ.	15	16.13
MAPEH	7	7.53
ESP	1	1.08
Total	93	100.00

Table 2 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents in terms of their field of specialization

Data shows that 14 or 15.05 percent of the respondents have English as their field of specialization, 12 or 12.90 specialize in Filipino, 13 or 13.98 have Science and Araling Panlipunan as the field of specialization, 18 or 19.35 percent specialize in Mathematics, 15 or 16.13, in Technology and Home Economics, 7 or 7.53 percent in MAPEH and one or 1.08 percent has ESP as specialization.

The data shows that most of the teachers are Mathematics majors and only a one has Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao as field of specialization.

Based on the documents received by the researcher, some teachers are teaching subjects that are not their field of specialization. According to DepEd Order No. 13, s. 1994 known as Guidelines for Matching Specialization in Teaching Preparation with

Teaching Assignments for Public School Teachers, a secondary school teacher should teach his/her major field of specialization. However, since the situation presented above is not as expected, the department find ways to fill the gap through the implementation of programs on teachers' upskilling and reskilling through Sulong Edukalidad. As mentioned in DO 50, s. 2020, the professional development priorities shall support the realization of the Department's goal of continuous upskilling and reskilling of teachers and school leaders that will result in better learning outcomes. In her speech during the launching of the program in 2019, Sec. Leonor B. Magtolis (2019) mentioned that the department is investing and giving full support to teachers for their in-service professional development, and provides the proper incentives through career progression and promotion opportunities as they develop their teaching proficiency. These programs were implemented from the central office down to the different schools in the country.

1.b Teaching Experience

Table 3
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents In terms of their Teaching Experience

Teaching Experience	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Less than 5 years	35	37.63
6 to 13 years	32	34.41
14 to 21 years	9	9.68
22 to 30 years	12	12.90
over 30 years	5	5.38
TOTAL	93	100.00

Table 3 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents in terms of their teaching experience. The distribution reveals that 37.63 percent or 35 teachers are new in the service with less than 5 years in the service, 34 percent or 32 teachers have served for 6-13 years in the organization while 9.68 percent or 9 teachers have 14-21 years of teaching experience, 12 teachers or 12.90 percent have served the organization for 22-30 years, and five teachers or 5.38 percent have served the Department for over 30 years. Those who have 3 years of service or more were awarded loyalty commendations due to their selfless commitment and dedication to their sworn duties and responsibilities. These awards given to teachers served as a motivation or encouragement for them to perform better and be more productive. Teachers who receive regular recognition and praise are more productive, are more engaged at work, are more likely to stay with their school and are more likely to receive higher satisfaction scores from students and parents (Department of Education, 2002).

Department Order No. 9, s. 2002 titled Establishing the Program on Awards and Incentives for Service Excellence (PRAISE) in the Department of Education pointed out the importance of recognizing the work of all the employees in the department as a

motivation for them to work for more. It aims to encourage, recognize and reward employees, individually or in groups, for their suggestion, innovative ideas, inventions, discoveries, superior accomplishments, heroic deeds, exemplary behavior, extraordinary acts or services in the interest and other personal efforts contributing to efficiency, economy and improvement in government operations which lead to organizational productivity (Department of Education, 2015).

Giving recognition to teachers usually happens quarterly, during the Teacher's Month celebration in October or during the Education Month celebration sometimes in December. This is based on the interview done with school heads.

1.c Teaching Loads

Table 4
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in Terms of their Teaching Loads

Teaching Loads	Frequency	Percentage
8 and above	18	19.35
7	23	24.73
6	38	40.86
5	10	10.75
below 5	4	4.30
Total	93	100.00

Table 4 shows the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents in terms of their teaching loads. The data reveals that 18 teachers or 19.35 percent have eight (8) teaching loads and 23 or 24.73 percent have seven (7) loads. These teachers are considered overloaded based on the prescribed number of teaching hours for teachers. Most or 40.86 percent of the teachers have six (6) teaching loads which is the required teaching loads for teachers. There are 15 teachers with less than the minimum required teaching loads for the teachers.

DM 291, s. 2008 known as Guidelines for the Implementation of CSC Resolution No. 080096 on Working Hours of Public School Teachers provides public school teachers are not exempt from the eight-hour workday provided for in RA 1880, where six (6) hours is devoted to teaching and the remaining two (2) hours for other academic work other than teaching. One (1) hour teaching is equivalent to one (1) teaching load (Department of Education, 2008). The above mandate was further clarified in DO 16, s. 2009 titled Addendum to DM 291, s. 2008 (Guidelines for the Implementation of CSC Resolution No. 080096 on Working Hours for Public School Teachers). The six (6) hours of actual classroom teaching shall cover the full teaching load of a teacher as indicated in the class program. Based on DepEd Memorandum No. 291, s. 2008, teaching loads including

advisorships and/or special assignments for the entire school year combined shall be considered as one teaching load.

In an interview conducted with the school heads, those who are underload are given non-teaching designations like designated guidance teacher, bookkeeper, disbursing officer, librarian, reading teacher, SSG adviser, canteen manager, Gulayan sa Paaralan Coordinator, LIS/BEIS Coordinator, school publication adviser, NDEP Coordinator, School DRRM Coordinator, School Information Coordinator, and the like. These ancillary assignments are given to teachers because of a lack of non-teaching personnel to handle them.

1.d Distance of Residence from School

Table 5
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Respondents in Terms of the Distance of Residence from School

Distance in Km	Frequency	Percentage
16 and above	15	16.13
11 to 15 km	9	9.68
6 to 10 km	18	19.35
1 to 5 km	33	35.48
less than 1 km	18	19.35
TOTAL	93	100.00

Table 5 displays the frequency and percentage distribution of the respondents in terms of the distance of residence from school. The data reveals that 15 or 16.13 percent live 16 km. or more away from the school, nine teachers or 9.68 percent live 11-15 km. away from the school, and 18 or 19.35 percent of the teachers' residence is 6-10 km from the school. Most or 35.48 percent of the teachers live 1-5 km. away from school. There are 18 teachers or 19.35 percent whose residence is less than 1 km. from the school.

This implies that more than half of the total teacher-respondents live near the school based on the distance traveled by the teacher every day. However, there are those who come from as far as 16 kilometers or more and patiently travel every day. According to them, they prefer to go home every afternoon so that they are with their families during the night. Besides traveling is fast and easy because the roads are already cemented and are categorized as "all weather roads".

1.e Level of ICT Competence

Table 6
Respondents' Level of ICT Competence

	ICT Competence	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1	Identify and define the functions of the main components and peripherals of the computer	3.18	Moderately Competent
2	Properly connect main components, configure peripherals, and install drivers when required	3.10	Moderately Competent
3	Organize and manage computer files, folders, and directories	3.37	Highly Competent
4	Use storage devices for storing and sharing files	3.39	Highly Competent
5	Use online and offline help facilities for troubleshooting, maintenance, and update of applications	3.00	Moderately Competent
6	Use a word processor to enter and edit text and images, format text, control margins, layout, and tables	3.26	Highly Competent
7	Use a calculation spreadsheet to enter and sort data, format cells into tables, use formulas, and create graphs	3.06	Moderately Competent
8	Use and enhance presentations by adding sound, customizing animation, and inserting images	3.09	Moderately Competent
9	Make an effective class presentation using the slides and LCD projector	3.30	Highly Competent
10	Acquire, crop, scale, color, and enhance digital images from websites, flash drives, cellphones, cameras, etc.	3.04	Moderately Competent
11	Play various media files, stitch together video footage and soundtracks, and add simple enhancements	2.94	Moderately Competent
12	Connect to the internet via dial-up or LAN	3.15	Moderately Competent
13	Configure and use web browser and help applications	3.00	Moderately Competent
14	Send and receive emails with attachments	3.87	Highly Competent
15	Effectively use synchronous and asynchronous web-based communication tools like messenger, teleconferencing, etc.	3.12	Moderately Competent

16	Distribute, share, publish, and print information sources – online and offline	3.22	Moderately Competent
17	Properly acknowledge information sources – online and offline	3.85	Highly Competent
18	Use electronic means of administering quizzes and examinations	2.94	Moderately Competent
19	Analyze assessment data using spreadsheets and statistical applications	3.03	Moderately Competent
20	Use emails, group sites, blogs, etc. for disseminating collecting information directly to students, colleagues, and parents	3.15	Moderately Competent
	Overall Weighted Mean	3.20	Moderately Competent

The table presents the Level of ICT competence of the respondents. As reflected in the table, the level of ICT competence of the respondents is described as “moderately competent” based on the overall weighted mean which is 3.20.

Specifically, the respondents are highly competent in organizing and managing computer files, folders, and directories; using storage devices for storing and sharing files; using a word processor to enter and edit text and images, format text, control margins, layout, and tables; making an effective class presentation using the slides and LCD projector; sending and receiving emails with attachments and properly acknowledging information sources – online and offline.

Additionally, the data shows that the respondents are “Moderately Competent” in using storage devices for storing and sharing files, distributing, sharing, publishing and printing information sources – online and offline, identifying and defining the functions of the main components and peripherals of the computer, connecting to the internet via dial-up or LAN, using emails, group sites, blogs, etc. for disseminating collecting information directly to students, colleagues and parents, effectively using synchronous and asynchronous web-based communication tools like messenger, teleconferencing, etc., properly connecting main components, configure peripherals and installing drivers when required, using and enhancing presentations by adding sound, customizing animation and inserting images, using a calculation spreadsheet to enter and sort data, format cells into tables, use formula and create graphs, acquiring, cropping, scaling, coloring and enhancing digital images from web sites, flash drives, cellphones, cameras, etc., and analyzing assessment data using spreadsheets and statistical applications.

They are “Fairly Competent” in the following competencies: use online and offline help facilities for troubleshooting, maintenance, and update of applications, configure and use web browsers and help applications, play various media files, stitch together video footage and soundtracks and add simple enhancements, and use electronic means of administering quizzes and examinations.

Results of the study reveal that teachers have basic knowledge of ICT and are described as moderately competent. However, this is not enough to say that teachers are already competent in ICT. Teachers need to be proficient in knowing where and when to use technology for teaching and other related tasks. Teachers' professional development is a key factor to the successful integration of computers in classroom teaching. Computer competence is defined as being able to handle a wide range of varying computer applications for various purposes. Similarly, educators who integrate technology with new teaching practices gained through professional training can transform the performance of the students. One of the biggest benefits of ICT training for teachers is the improvement in the teaching and learning experience. With the use of technology, teachers can create more interactive and engaging lessons that cater to different learning styles. This can lead to better retention of information and improved academic performance for students. Additionally, ICT training can help teachers stay up-to-date with the latest teaching methods and tools, allowing them to provide a more effective and efficient learning experience for their students. Hence, there is really a need for teachers to improve their ICT competence (Caluza et al., 2017).

2. Teachers' Level of Teaching Efficacy
 2. a Student Engagement

Table 7
Respondents' Level of Teaching Efficacy In Terms of Student Engagement

	Items	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Level of Efficacy
1	How much can you do to get through to the most difficult students?	4.20	A Great Deal	Highly Efficacious
2	How much can you do to help your students think critically?	4.31	A Great Deal	Highly Efficacious
3	How much can you do to motivate students who show low interest in the school work	4.27	A Great Deal	Highly Efficacious
4	How much can you do to get students to believe they can do well in school work?	4.39	A Great Deal	Highly Efficacious
5	How much can you do to help students value learning?	4.45	A Great Deal	Highly Efficacious
6	How much can you do to foster student creativity?	4.24	A Great Deal	Highly Efficacious
7	How much can you do to improve the understanding of a student who is falling?	4.32	A Great Deal	Highly Efficacious
8	How much can you assist families in helping their children do well in school?	3.89	Quite Bit	Moderately Efficacious
	OVERALL WEIGHTED MEAN	4.26	A Great Deal	Highly Efficacious

The table presents the respondents' level of teaching efficacy particularly in terms of student engagement.

As shown on the table, the respondents are “Highly Efficacious” as reflected in the overall weighted mean of 4.26. The data in particular reveal that the teachers help students value learning, get students to believe they can do well in school work, improve the understanding of a student who is falling, help students think critically, foster student creativity, get through to the most difficult students to a “Great Deal.”

The data also shows that the teachers are “moderately efficacious” in assisting families in helping their children do well in school.

According to Stephens (2015), in order to increase student engagement, instructors with a higher sense of academic efficacy are more likely to use proactive, positive, and solution-focused pedagogy. Similarly, Van Uden et al. (2013) hypothesized that instructors' sense of efficacy can positively influence their affective orientation toward their students, resulting in increased student engagement. These studies emphasized the critical role of teachers in shaping students' educational experiences.

2.b Instructional Strategies

Table 8
Teachers’ Level of Efficiency in Terms of Instructional Strategies

	Items	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Level of Efficacy
1	How well can you respond to difficult questions from your students?	4.25	A Great Deal	Highly Efficacious
2	How much can you gauge student comprehension of what you have taught?	4.24	A Great Deal	Highly Efficacious
3	To what extent can you craft good questions for your students?	4.22	A Great Deal	Highly Efficacious
4	How much can you do to adjust your lessons to the proper level for individual students?	4.24	A Great Deal	Highly Efficacious
5	How much can you use a variety of assessment strategies?	4.14	Quite Bit	Moderately Efficacious
6	To what extent can you provide an alternative explanation or example when students are confused?	4.24	A Great Deal	Highly Efficacious
7	How well can you implement alternative strategies in your classroom?	4.08	Quite Bit	Moderately Efficacious

8	How well can you provide appropriate challenges for very capable students?	4.17	Quite Bit	Moderately Efficacious
	OVERALL WEIGHTED MEAN	4.20	A Great Deal	Highly Efficacious

Table 8 the respondents' level of teaching efficacy in terms of instructional strategies.

As shown in the table, the respondents are “Highly Efficacious” as indicated by the overall weighted mean of 4.20. According to the teachers, to a *great deal*, they respond to difficult questions from your students, gauge student comprehension of what you have taught, adjust your lessons to the proper level for individual students, provide an alternative explanation or example when students are confused, can craft good questions for your students.

However, when asked about their ability in providing appropriate challenges for very capable students, using a variety of assessment strategies, and providing appropriate challenges for very capable students, the responded “*Quite a Bit*” which indicates that they are moderately efficacious along these areas.

In a study of Yilmaz (2020), he discovered that teachers with a growth mindset employ instructional strategies more effectively than those with a fixed mindset. Furthermore, adopting a growth mindset increases teachers' efficacy in instructional strategies. Teachers who can use different approaches and provide various justifications or examples demonstrate high levels of pedagogical effectiveness. Additionally, using a variety of assessment techniques allows teachers to accurately assess students' understanding. Overall, these implications emphasize the importance of teachers creating dynamic, engaging, and productive learning environments that meet the diverse needs of their students.

2.c Classroom Management

Table 9
Teachers' Efficiency Level In Terms of Classroom Management

	Items	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Level of Efficacy
1	How much can you do to control disruptive behavior in the classroom?	4.22	A Great Deal	Highly Efficacious
2	To what extent can you make your expectations clear about student behavior?	4.19	Quite Bit	Moderately Efficacious
3	How well can you establish routines to keep activities running smoothly?	4.17	Quite Bit	Moderately Efficacious

4	How much can you do to get children to follow classroom rules?	4.33	A Great Deal	Highly Efficacious
5	How much can you do to calm a student who is disruptive or noisy?	4.24	A Great Deal	Highly Efficacious
6	How well can you establish a classroom management system with each group of students?	4.29	A Great Deal	Highly Efficacious
7	How well can you keep a few problem students from running an entire lesson?	4.12	Quite Bit	Moderately Efficacious
8	How well can you respond to a defiant student?	4.05	Quite Bit	Moderately Efficacious
	OVERALL WEIGHTED MEAN	4.20	A Great Deal	Highly Efficacious

The data presents the respondents level of teaching efficacy in classroom management..

As shown on the table, the respondents responded “A Great Deal’ to the following items: getting children to follow classroom rules in, establishing a classroom management system with each group of students, calming a student who is disruptive or noisy, and controlling disruptive behavior in the classroom. When asked to what extent can they make their expectations clear about student behavior, how well can they establish routines to keep activities running smoothly, how well can they keep a few problem students from running an entire lesson, and how well can they respond to a defiant student, the teachers' response was “Quite a Bit”.

These emphasized how crucial the role of teachers in upholding classroom discipline, encouraging good behavior, and boosting students' self-efficacy. It follows that teachers who are strong in these areas are more likely to give their students a secure, encouraging, and stimulating learning environment, which will eventually improve student engagement and academic results. In surveys conducted by Stueber (2019), teachers indicated that instructional skills and classroom management were essential to help with students' safety and disruptive behaviors in the classroom. And since teachers must establish the best learning environment possible in the classroom, effective management of it is necessary.

Table 10
Summary of Teachers level of Teaching Efficacy

	Items	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description	Level of Efficacy
1	Student Engagement	4.26	A Great Deal	Highly Efficacious
2	Instructional Strategies	4.20	A Great Deal	Highly Efficacious

3	Classroom Management	4.20	A Great Deal	Highly Efficacious
	OVERALL WEIGHTED MEAN	4.22	A Great Deal	Highly Efficacious

Table 3.d presents the summary of espondents' level of teaching efficacy. As shown in the table, the respondents are "Highly Efficacious" as reflected in the overall weighted mean of 4.22.

Further, the data reveals that the teachers are very efficacious in student engagement which has the highest weighted mean of 4.26 followed by instructional strategies and classroom management with a weighted mean of 4.20.

The findings of this study confirm the findings of other researchers on teaching efficacy. Teachers' beliefs about their skills or capabilities have been thought to be attributed to effective teaching because they influence "the way they learn to teach and their perceptions, judgments, decision-making, and actions in the classroom" (Stephens, 2015; van Uden et al., 2013). Therefore, teacher efficacy beliefs are considered to be "stronger indicators for predicting their teaching behaviors". In this sense, certain studies have already found that more efficacious teachers can cope with difficult situations easily, are good at planning and organization, use instructional strategies more effectively, sustain student engagement and motivation, maintain the continuity of the task, are good at teaching particular subjects, are better in classroom management, and are more open to innovations. Moreover, in the literature, a higher level of teacher efficacy has been steadily found to lead to higher levels of student achievement as well as better performance of teachers in the classroom.

3. Significant Relationship Between Level of Teaching Efficacy and Profile

3.a Student Engagement

Table 11
Results of the Test of Significant Relationship Between the Teachers' Level of Teaching Efficacy in Student Engagement and their Profile

Teachers' Level of Teaching Efficacy in Terms of Student Engagement and their Profile	Significance of X ² or p-value	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Field of Specialization	0.793	p>0.05	Accept H _o	Not Significant
Teaching Experience	0.816	p>0.05	Accept H _o	Not Significant

Teaching Loads and Other Assignments	0.944	p>0.05	Accept H _o	Not Significant
Distance of Residence from the School	0.062	p>0.05	Accept H _o	Not Significant
Level of ICT Competence	0.136	p>0.05	Accept H _o	Not Significant

Table 11 presents the results of the test of significant relationship between the teachers' teaching efficacy in student engagement and their profile.

The results show that the significance of Chi-square (X^2) or the p-values are greater than 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted data 0.05 level of significance. Thus, there is no significant relationship between the teachers' teaching efficacy in student engagement and their profile. It implies that the teachers' teaching experience, teaching load, place of residence and ICT competence have no significant effect on the teachers' teaching efficacy in student engagement.

3.b Instructional Strategies

Table 12
Results of the Test of Significant Relationship Between the Teachers' Teaching Efficacy in Instructional Strategies and their Profile

Teachers' Level of Teaching Efficacy in Terms of Instructional and their Profile	Significance of X^2 or p-value	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Field of Specialization	0.847	p>0.05	Accept H _o	Not Significant
Teaching Experience	0.756	p>0.05	Accept H _o	Not Significant
Teaching Loads and Other Assignments	0.168	p>0.05	Accept H _o	Not Significant
Distance of Residence from the School	0.002	P<0.05	Reject H _o	Significant
Level of ICT Competence	0.313	p>0.05	Accept H _o	Not Significant

The results of the test of significant relationship between the teachers' teaching efficacy in instructional strategies and their profile are presented in Table 12.

Its reveals a Chi-square or the p-values that are greater than 0.05 except for distance of residence from the school. This signifies the acceptance of the null hypothesis at 0.05 significance level meaning, there is no significant relationship between the

teachers' teaching efficacy in instructional strategies and their field of specialization, teaching experience, teaching loads and other assignments and the level of ICT competence. This finding is corroborated by Pescuela (2015) who found that length of teaching is not a predictive factor because both novice and experienced teachers support one another in their roles as they work toward improved job performance in the educational system, which is based on effectiveness, timeliness, and efficiency.

However, there is a significant relationship between the teachers' efficacy in instructional strategies and the distance of residence from the school. It implies that the distance of residence of the teachers from the school significantly affects their teaching efficacy in instructional strategies.

3.c Classroom Management

Table 13
Results of Significant Relationship Between the Teachers' Level of Teaching Efficacy in Terms of Classroom Management and Their Profile

Teachers' Level of Teaching Efficacy in Terms of Classroom Management and their Profile	Significance of X^2 or p-value	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Field of Specialization	0.070	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Teaching Experience	0.935	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Teaching Loads and Other Assignments	0.312	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Distance of Residence from the School	0.281	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Level of ICT Competence	0.067	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant

Table 13 displays the results of the test of a significant relationship between the teachers' teaching efficacy in classroom management and their profile.

It is evident from the results that the significance of X^2 or the p-values is greater than 0.05. For this reason, the null hypothesis is accepted at a 0.05 level of significance. As a result, there is no significant relationship between the teachers' teaching efficacy in classroom management and their profile. It indicates that the profile variables enumerated in the table do not significantly affect the teachers' teaching efficacy in classroom management. Secondary school teachers of Quirino District are efficacious regardless of their field of specialization, teaching experience, teaching loads and other assignments, distance of residence from the school, and ICT competence

This result contradicts the studies of Shoulders and Krei (2015) which showed a significant mean difference between years of teaching experience and self-efficacy in

instructional practices and classroom management. The follow-up post hoc analysis showed a difference between teachers with 0-4 years of teaching experience and teachers with 15 or more years of experience in both efficacies in instructional practices and classroom management. Also, the study by Soodak and Podell (1997) found teachers with 20+ years of experience more efficient than beginning teachers, but there was no difference in efficacy between the beginning teachers (0-4 years of experience) and more established teachers (5-14 years of experience).

4. Teachers' Level of Motivation

Table 14
Respondents' Level of Motivation

	Items	Weighted Mean	Qualitative Description
1	I am proud I am a teacher	3.88	Strongly Agree
2	I like to work toward some goals that I have to set for myself	3.80	Strongly Agree
3	I work when I'm told	2.69	Agree
4	I feel nervous when giving a talk before a group	2.73	Agree
5	I maintain a smooth relationship with my co-teachers in my own standards	3.39	Strongly Agree
6	I like to see others work under pressure by their superior/head	1.57	Strongly Disagree
7	I mind criticism seriously	2.41	Disagree
8	I teach when I am in the mood	1.65	Strongly Disagree
9	I work late when I am told to do so	1.85	Disagree
10	I respond negatively to my superior	1.52	Strongly Disagree
11	I feel tired of teaching	1.66	Strongly Disagree
12	I envy teachers who receive an award	1.99	Disagree
13	I submit reports on or before the deadline	3.15	Agree
14	I give rewards to students who follow instructions/rules	3.34	Strongly Agree
15	I like my profession more than anything else	3.29	Strongly Agree
16	I like to work with limitations	2.46	Disagree
17	I am not bothered when students' evaluations are poor	1.86	Disagree
18	I compliment superiors who are target-oriented	3.24	Agree
19	I delegate my work to others for personal welfare	1.82	Disagree
20	I conduct meetings with parents regularly	3.03	Agree
21	I try to achieve my maximum level of performance even if students cannot	2.90	Agree

22	I feel nervous when my superiors come to my room	2.46	Disagree
23	I ask support from the community for my own benefit alone	1.62	Strongly Disagree
24	I stay in school beyond hours	2.73	Agree
25	I avoid rivalry towards promotions	3.02	Agree
26	I expect much from my students	2.94	Agree
27	I take responsibility without being told	3.39	Strongly Agree
28	I know everything about my profession	2.98	Agree
29	I appreciate resourceful teachers	3.73	Strongly Agree
30	I want students to learn easily	3.71	Strong Agree
	Overall Weighted Mean	2.69	Agree

The table presents the respondents' level of motivation. The table reveals that the respondents are moderately motivated as shown by their strong agreement with most of the items with an overall weighted mean of 2.69.

Teachers “Strongly Agree” to the following statements: I am proud I am a teacher, I like to work toward some goal that I have to set for myself, I maintain a smooth relationship with my co-teachers in my standards, I give rewards to students who follow instructions/rules, I like my profession more than anything else, I take responsibility without being told, I appreciate resourceful teachers, I want students to learn easily.

They also “Agree” that they work when told, they feel nervous when giving a talk before a group, they submit reports on or before the deadline, they complimented superiors who are target oriented, they conduct meetings with parents regularly, they try to achieve my maximum level of performance even if students cannot, they stay in school beyond hours, they avoid rivalry towards promotions, they expect much from their students, and they know everything about their profession.

However, they “Disagree” that they mind criticism seriously, work late when told to do so, envy teachers who receive an award, like to work with limitations, are not bothered when students' evaluation is poor, delegate their work to others for personal welfare, and feel nervous when superiors come to their room, Much more, they “Strongly Disagree” that they like to see others work under pressure by their superior/head, teach when I am in the mood, respond negatively to my superior, feel tired teaching, and ask support from the community for their benefit alone. The result of the study suggest that secondary school teachers of Quirino District are not fully motivated in their chosen profession. Looking closely at factors determining the quality of teaching, it is evident that the motivation factor plays a significant role because even if teachers are well-trained and have good experience, they are less likely to teach well if they are not motivated. If a teacher is not motivated, he/she will not be committed to his/her work. Likewise, a teacher who is not motivated is less likely to be satisfied with his/ her job. As defined by Ololube (2006), motivation is an attitude or desire to do something. A teacher's motivation, therefore, refers to the teacher's attitude or desire to work. Job satisfaction is one's feeling or state of mind regarding the nature of one's work. Teachers' job satisfaction therefore

refers to their feelings or attitudes regarding their work. He further explains that job satisfaction and motivation to work are very essential in the lives of teachers because they form the fundamental reason for working.

Results of previous studies further reveal that teacher motivation is an essential component to enhance classroom effectiveness. As students' learning outcomes are highly dependent on the quality of instruction, teaching effectiveness has been explored in terms of teaching styles, teacher approaches to teaching, teaching practice and instruction behaviors in relation to teacher motivation factors (Han & Yin, 2016).

5. Significant Relationship Between Motivation and Profile

Table 15
Results of Significant Relationship Between the Teachers' Level of Motivation and their Profile

Teachers' Level of Motivation and the Following Profile	Significance of X^2 or p-value	Analysis	Decision	6. Remarks
Field of Specialization	0.647	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Teaching Experience	0.821	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Teaching Loads and Other Assignments	0.440	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Distance of Residence from the School	0.103	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Level of ICT Competence	0.673	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant

The results of significant relationship between the teachers' level of motivation and their profile are displayed in Table 15.

The table reflects that the significance of X^2 or the p-values is greater than 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted at a 0.05 significance level. Thus, there is no significant relationship between the teachers' level of motivation and their profile. It implies that the teachers' level of motivation is not significantly affected by their profile. This is similar to the findings in a study of Sala (2020) conducted in Negros Oriental Division on the motivational factors of teachers' performance, that teachers' sex, educational qualification, and teaching experience are significantly related to their job performance based on the RPMS, however, concerning the extent to which teachers are motivated by the motivational factors, teachers' profile was found to be insignificant.

6. Teachers Level of Performance

Table 16
Frequency and Percentage of the Respondents According to Performance for the Last Two Years

Performance	SY 2019-2020		SY 2020-2021		Average	
	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Outstanding (4.500 – 5.000)	31	33.33	76	81.72	107	57.53
Very Satisfactory (3.500 - 4.499)	62	66.67	17	18.28	79	42.47
Satisfactory (2.500 – 3.499)	0	0	0	0	0	0
Unsatisfactory (1.500 – 2.499)	0	0	0	0	0	0
Poor (below 1.499)	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	93	100	93	100	186	100

Table 16 reveals the frequency and percentage of the respondents according to their performance for the last two years. It shows that for the school year 2019-2020, 31 teachers or 33.33 percent have an Outstanding performance and most or 66.67 percent have a Very Satisfactory performance. For the school year 2020-2021, the majority, or 81.72 percent of the teachers have an Outstanding performance and 17, or 18.28 percent were rated Very Satisfactory. The finding revealed that all the teachers of Quirino District are performing well based on their performance ratings.

Based on the result of the Individual RPMS, teachers of Quirino District are well knowledgeable in terms of the content knowledge and pedagogy of the subject area they are teaching; they are excellent in managing the learning environment and the diversity of learners; they are very good in contextualizing and localizing curriculum and planning to suit the needs of the learners. The teachers develop and utilize creative and appropriate instructional plans, use a variety of appropriate assessment strategies to monitor and evaluate learning and regularly monitor and provide feedback on learners' understanding of content. Students' learning outcomes is the goal of planning, assessing and reporting. The sequence of learning experiences that teachers provide should build on what students already know and should be designed to ensure that they progress through the Stages identified in the learning continuum. As students participate in a range

of learning experiences, teachers make judgement about what students know, what they can do and what they understand.; and they rated very satisfactory in the assessment of learning acquired by the learners and reported early its outcome to parents or guardians for immediate action.

Table 16 disclosed the level of teachers' job performance, which is a central construct in the field of work both in any organizations. It refers to the ways individuals perform their jobs. Having a high job performance means that teachers have the ability to combine relevant inputs for the enhancement of the teaching and learning process and improvement of student learning. Moreover, the above reflected findings conform with the results of the local studies among others which all revealed that majority of the teachers have "very satisfactory" ratings as then shown in their performance evaluation system (Comighud & Arevalo, 2020).

7. Significant Relationship Between Performance and Profile

Table 17
Results of the Test of Significant Relationship Between the Teachers' Level of Performance and their Profile

Teachers' Level of Performance and the Following Profile	Significance of X ² or p-value	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Field of Specialization	0.314	p>0.05	Accept H _o	Not Significant
Teaching Experience	0.592	p>0.05	Accept H _o	Not Significant
Teaching Loads and Other Assignments	0.769	p>0.05	Accept H _o	Not Significant
Distance of Residence from the School	0.440	p>0.05	Accept H _o	Not Significant
Level of ICT Competence	0.268	p>0.05	Accept H _o	Not Significant

Table 17 exhibits the results of the test of significant relationship between the teachers' level of performance and their profile.

The results show that the significance of X² or the p-values is greater than 0.05. This signifies the acceptance of the null hypothesis at a 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, there is no significant relationship between the teachers' level of performance and their profile. It means that the teachers' profiles do not significantly affect their performance.

8. Significant Relationship Between and Among Teaching Efficiency, Motivation and Performance

Table 18
Results of Significant Relationships Between and Among the Teachers' Level of Efficacy, Level of Motivation, and Level of Performance

Variables	The computed Value of r	Significance of r or 9. p-value	Analysis	Decision	Remarks
Teachers' Level of Efficacy and Level of Motivation	-0.028	0.790	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Teachers' Level of Efficacy and Level of Performance	0.152	0.148	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant
Teachers' Level of Motivation and Level of Performance	-0.075	0.479	$p > 0.05$	Accept H_0	Not Significant

Table 18 shows the results of the test of significant relationship between and among the teachers' level of teaching efficacy, level of motivation, and level of performance.

It is revealed from the results that the teachers' level of efficacy and level of motivation, and teachers' level of motivation and level of performance are negatively correlated as evidenced by the negative value of r. It means that as one variable increases, the other decreases. On one hand, the teachers' level of efficacy and their level of performance are positively correlated which means that the two variables both increases or decreases.

However, to test the strength of relationship, the p-value is used. The results show that the p-values are greater than 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted at 0.05 level of significance. Thus, there is no significant relationship between and among the teachers' level of teaching efficacy, level of motivation, and level of performance. It implies that the teachers' level of teaching efficacy and level of motivation do not significantly affect their level of performance as well as their level of motivation has no significant bearing on their teaching efficacy.

This is in contrast with a study that explored the motivations for becoming a teacher, teachers' self-efficacy, and the relationship between motivations and teacher self-efficacy using data from the TALIS 2018 among teachers with six or more years of teaching experience. Results indicate that motivations, which were more intrinsic and altruistic, for becoming a teacher are positively correlated to teacher self-efficacy in classroom management, instruction, student engagement, and multicultural classrooms.

The strongest relationship was between motivation and self-efficacy in multicultural classrooms; the smallest relationship was between motivation and self-efficacy in classroom management. Extrinsic motivations had limited relationships to self-efficacy (Calkins et al., 2024).

Conclusions

The study sought to understand various aspects of the secondary school teachers in the Quirino District, Quirino, Isabela, by exploring their profiles, teaching efficacy, motivation, and performance. The investigation aimed to answer key questions about the teachers' fields of specialization, teaching experience, teaching loads, distance of residence from the school, level of ICT knowledge, and how these factors relate to their teaching efficacy, motivation, and performance.

The results highlights that the teachers in the Quirino District come from diverse educational backgrounds with varying length of service. Most teachers adhered to the required teaching loads, although a notable number fell below this requirement. In terms of residence, most teachers lived within a 1-5 km radius from their schools, which suggests that commuting distances were generally manageable. In regard to their ICT competence, their moderate competence indicate a potential area for further development.

With regard teaching efficacy, the teachers exhibited a high level of efficacy, particularly in student engagement, instructional strategies, and classroom management. However, no significant relationship between teaching efficacy and the teachers' profiles was found. The motivation of the teachers was moderately high. There is no significant relationship between motivation and the teachers' profiles. The teachers of the five public secondary schools in Quirino District perform "Very Satisfactorily."

Moreover, the study found no significant relationships between teaching efficacy, motivation, and performance indicating that the levels of teaching efficacy and motivation do not significantly affect the teachers' performance, and vice versa.

On a final note, while the teachers of the Quirino District demonstrate high teaching efficacy and satisfactory performance, these attributes appear to be independent of their demographic profiles. The findings suggest that professional development efforts should focus on enhancing teaching practices uniformly across the board rather than targeting specific demographic groups. Enhancing ICT competence and addressing any disparities in teaching loads could further improve teaching effectiveness in the district.

Recommendations

In light of the findings and conclusion, the following recommendations are forwarded:

1. Since not all the teachers teach their field of specialization, there is a need for them to go for upskilling and reskilling.

2. As mentioned in the interview conducted among the teachers, there were those who are considered underload base on the prescribed number of actual teaching loads stated in the Magna Carta for Teachers.

3. In as much as the teachers were found to be moderately competent in ICT, the administrators should send them to ICT seminars and training to make them more competent in integrating ICT in their teaching and in return help their students to become competent as well. Teachers who are highly competent in the technology can also provide technical assistance to those who are not through mentoring or coaching.

4. Learning resources and facilities should be provided to make the teachers become more efficacious and highly motivated to deliver the goods to the students.

5. A differentiated supervisory program is proposed as Chapter 6 in this manuscript.

6. Areas for Further Research

- (i) This research focused only on teaching efficacy, motivation and performance in relation to the respondents' profile. There is a need to add other variables that can contribute in the desired quality of education in the country.
- (ii) This study focused only in the district of Quirino, Isabela. Further research on a wider in scope may be conducted as basis for crafting laws, orders, memorandum and other issuances to improve teachers' performances.
- (iii) The same study can be conducted among the elementary school teachers of the same district to strengthen the result of this study and for comparison.
- (iv) This study involved only teachers. Further research could include other stakeholders of education like students and parents in order to get their views on the topic the role of the level of efficacy, motivation and performance in relation to the teacher's profile on their job performance in secondary schools.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This research adhered to ethical principles that respect the rights and dignity of all participants. Before the data collection process began, the study was submitted for approval to the Schools Division Superintendent of Isabela, in compliance with institutional guidelines. Upon receiving approval, the researcher sought informed consent from all participants, ensuring that they understood the purpose of the study, their voluntary participation, and their right to withdraw at any time without penalty.

The confidentiality and anonymity of the respondents were strictly maintained. No personal identifiers were used in the reporting of data, and the results were presented in aggregate form to avoid any risk of identifying individual participants. The researcher also made sure that no sensitive or personal information beyond what was necessary for the research was collected.

Additionally, the study ensured that all information was handled with integrity and in accordance with the ethical standards set forth by the research institution and relevant academic guidelines. Data was collected and analyzed in a manner that protected the participants' privacy, while also complying with the Philippine Data Privacy Act of 2012.

The researcher has ensured that the data gathered was solely for academic purposes and will be used to improve teaching practices and contribute to the development of educational reforms. There were no conflicts of interest or undue influence in the conduct of the study.

Acknowledgements

This research would not have been completed without the help and support of innumerable people who in one way or the other extended their valuable assistance. The researcher would like to express her sincere gratitude, appreciation, and thanks to the following people:

To Dr. Salome S. Cariño, Chairman of the Oral Defense Panel and graduate school professor, for her assistance and support throughout the completion of the study;

To her thesis advisor, Dr. Lucila B. Aggari, for her unwavering encouragement, enthusiasm, and insightful remarks and advice that helped make this research come to reality;

To Drs. Gilbert N. Tong, Vilma C. Cabrera, Charina G. Alejo, Jocelyn M. Claravall, Rodel V. Macapuy, and Mrs. Benedicta M. Uy, members of the Oral Defense panel, for their support and invaluable comments and suggestions that helped improve this piece of work;

To the Saint Ferdinand College Graduate School professors for sharing their knowledge with the writer during her post graduate course. Likewise to the very accommodating secretary of the Graduate School, Mrs. Benelyn P. Jamora.

To the Schools Division of Isabela, through the SDS, Dr. Madelyn L. Macalling and Dr. Maribel M. Ancheta, the Quirino District PSDS, for granting her permission to conduct the study in the Quirino District and for voluntarily supplying the data required for this investigation.

To the Principals and teachers of Dolores Integrated School, Rizal Comprehensive National High School, Sto. Domingo Integrated School, Villa Cacho Integrated School and to Quirino National High School, for extending their support and cooperation and for allowing the researcher to conduct her study in their respective schools and for their honest responses and mutual cooperation in answering the survey questionnaire as respondents of the study.

To Dr. Michael T. Borromeo, her school head, for all of his kindness, support, and care, as well as for the information and ideals he imparted that aided in her professional development.

To her precious colleagues in Quirino National High School -Senior High Department, Mr. Aljun D. Cadorna, Mr. Jodel E. Agbayani, and Mrs. Mary Jane P. Gumangan, who have been very supportive and very encouraging;

To her beloved parents Mr. Victor B. Nagum (+) and Mrs. Francisca D. Nagum, to her loving siblings, Mr. Edgar D. Nagum, Mr. Victor D. Nagum Jr., Mrs.

Zeniabel N. Martinez, and Ms. Francivic D. Nagum, for their love and support, and for inspiring the writer in her academic journey;

To her nieces and nephews: Gayle, Ajjieh, Jardine, Alexis, Chrisjun, and Chrisjem. And to her bundles of joy: Jelove, Nisha-el, and Franceska, for their assistance;

Finally, to the Almighty Jesus Christ, who is above all, for answering her prayers, providing her with courage, wisdom, and knowledge, for being the source of all, and for giving her divine guidance and wisdom. Forevermore, He is worthy of all honor.

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